

1 Tectonostratigraphy of the Mérida Massif reveals a new
2 Cadomian suture zone exposure in Gondwana (SW Iberia)

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16 **ABSTRACT**

17 Neoproterozoic and Paleozoic rocks of the Mérida Massif (SW Iberia) have been grouped
18 into tectonostratigraphic units. Each unit is separated from the rest ones by either crustal-
19 scale thrusts and/or extensional detachments. The lowermost unit (Magdalena Gneisses;
20 lower plate) has continental crust affinity, and rest below a mafic-ultramafic ensemble,
21 referred to as the Mérida Ophiolite (suture zone). The Serie Negra Group constitutes a
22 unit with continental crust affinity (Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit; upper plate) located
23 on top of the Mérida Ophiolite. A carbonate-rich succession (Carija Unit) occupies the
24 uppermost structural position. Structural and isotopic data suggest that this suture zone

25 was formed during the Cadomian Orogeny. Superimposed shortening during the late
26 Paleozoic formed upright to NE-verging folds and thrusts that affected this suture zone
27 and juxtaposed it onto Ordovician strata during the Variscan Orogeny. The Mérida
28 Ophiolite represents a new Cadomian suture zone exposure in the Gondwanan realm of
29 the Iberian Massif, but its root zone is yet to be identified. This ophiolite shares a far-
30 travelled nature with other Cadomian and Variscan suture zone exposures in Iberia,
31 making the latter a piece of lithosphere built through inland transference of allochthonous
32 terranes from peri-Gondwana onto mainland Gondwana during the Neoproterozoic-
33 Cambrian and the Devonian-Carboniferous periods.

34

35 **Keywords:** Cadomian tectonics; Suture zone; Ophiolite; Variscan tectonics; SW Iberian
36 Massif

37

38 **1. Introduction**

39 Suture zone exposures related to the Cadomian Orogeny affecting the sections of
40 peri-Gondwana preserved in Europe and North Africa (Neoproterozoic – Cambrian) are
41 scarce in the geological record (El Hadi et al. 2010; Kounov et al. 2012; Arenas et al.
42 2018), but provide important constraints on the geodynamic and tectonic evolution of
43 peri-Gondwana. However, suture zones of this age are commonly covered by thick
44 sedimentary sequences deposited on the margin of Gondwana after suturing, if not
45 reworked or even reactivated, and thus blurred, during younger geodynamic cycles such
46 as the Variscan and Alpine. Before extensive, more oriented research can be performed
47 in cases like this, a proper introduction to the main features of a suture zone is essential.
48 In this manuscript we discuss the general setting of a new Cadomian suture zone in the

49 Iberian section of peri-Gondwana, and what are the main elements supporting its
50 existence.

51 Here we present a new geological map, cross-sections and structural analysis of
52 the Mérida Massif (Iberia) and distinguish its main tectonostratigraphic units and their
53 relationships. Lithological ensembles for each unit have been grouped according to their
54 structural position, crustal affinity and tectonometamorphic evolution. The resulting
55 tectonostratigraphy reveals a previously unrecognized nappe structure (Abalos et al.
56 1991; Azor et al. 1994; Ribeiro et al. 2010; Díez Fernández and Arenas 2015; Díez
57 Fernández et al. 2019). It also adds another ophiolite and suture zone exposure to the set
58 that features the Iberian Massif, thus strengthening the notion of the Iberian domain of
59 Gondwana as a region built through a series of suturing events.

60

61 **2. Geological setting**

62 The Iberian Massif constitutes the southernmost exposure of the Variscan Orogen
63 in Europe (Fig. 1), which resulted from the progressive collision of Gondwana, Laurussia
64 and their respective pericontinental terranes during the Devonian and Carboniferous
65 periods (Ribeiro et al. 2007; Martínez Catalán et al. 2009; Simancas et al. 2013; Díez
66 Fernández et al. 2016; Shaw and Johnston 2016). The current structure of the Iberian
67 Massif is the result of three orogenic cycles. Gondwana was affected by long-lived
68 subduction under its periphery during the Neoproterozoic and Lower Paleozoic (D'Lemos
69 et al. 1990; Quesada 1990; Nance et al. 1991; Eguíluz et al. 2000; Chantaine et al. 2001;
70 Linnemann et al. 2007; Pereira et al. 2007), its northern paleomargin bearing evidence of
71 arc-related magmatism (Dorr et al. 2002; Bandrés et al. 2004; Drost et al. 2004; Henriques
72 et al. 2015; Rubio-Ordóñez et al. 2015), basin development in active settings (Linnemann
73 et al. 2000; Linnemann et al. 2007; Fuenlabrada et al. 2012; Fernández-Suárez et al. 2013;

74 Pereira 2015; Fuenlabrada et al. 2016; Rojo-Pérez et al. 2019), and contractional and
75 extensional deformation (Balé and Brun 1989; Strachan and Taylor 1990; Eguíluz et al.
76 2000; Kröner et al. 2000; Bandres et al. 2002; Expósito et al. 2003; Simancas et al. 2004;
77 Díaz García 2006; Díez Fernández et al. 2019), all of which are collectively referred to
78 as Cadomian Orogeny (cycle). The external section of Gondwana facing such subduction
79 was involved in the Variscan cycle, whose onset and culmination may correspond to an
80 extensional event that led to the opening of oceanic basins (e.g., Rheic Ocean; Linnemann
81 et al. 2007; Nance et al. 2010), and the raise of the Variscan Orogen after their suturing
82 (Matte 1991; Franke 2000; Ballèvre et al. 2009; Martínez Catalán et al. 2009),
83 respectively. The Iberian Massif contains Cenozoic mountain ranges formed during the
84 Alpine cycle (e.g., de Vicente and Vegas 2009). Some of them occur at the boundaries of
85 the Iberian micro-plate (e.g., Pyrenees, Betics), while others occupy intra-plate positions.
86 Both are the result of plate tectonics in the Mediterranean domain as well as of distributed
87 strain upon Africa-Europe convergence (Dewey et al. 1989; Jolivet et al. 2008; de Vicente
88 et al. 2018).

89 The Mérida Massif is located in the SW part of the Iberian Massif (Fig. 2).
90 Previous studies have suggested that its composition and current structure is the result of
91 Cadomian, Variscan, and Alpine tectonics (Gonzalo 1987, 1989; Bandrés 2001; Insúa
92 Márquez et al. 2003). This massif includes an extensive exposure of Neoproterozoic and
93 Lower Paleozoic rocks (Fig. 3), and represents a good opportunity to study Cadomian
94 tectonics and the interference of subsequent orogenic cycles. Mapping of its bedrock
95 geology has provided different outcomes over the years (Roso de Luna and Hernández
96 Pacheco 1950; Gonzalo 1987; Bandrés 2001; Insúa Márquez et al. 2003). Although
97 poor exposure may explain some variation, most of it seems to derive from
98 contrasting criteria followed during mapping. The Mérida Massif, although relatively

99 small in size, is characterized by a significantly rich variety of rocks, making it difficult
100 to establish coherent lithological groups to be mapped. Deformation in this area includes
101 the development of foliations, folds, faults, and shear zones, some of which are coeval to
102 pervasive metamorphism (Gonzalo 1987, 1989; Bandrés et al. 2000; Bandrés 2001).

103

104 **3. Tectonostratigraphy**

105 In this section, we provide a brief description of the main lithological associations
106 we have established in the Mérida Massif (Fig. 3). Grouping is focused on recognition of
107 major tectonic blocks intervening in Cadomian and Variscan tectonics (Fig. 4). Rocks
108 included into each tectonostratigraphic unit meet the following grouping criteria: (i)
109 similar structural position at regional scale, (ii) the ensemble shows either continental or
110 oceanic crust affinity, (iii) equivalent tectonometamorphic evolution, and (iv) they are
111 separated from other units by either a major mechanical boundary (i.e., fault or ductile
112 shear zone) or a major stratigraphic discontinuity (e.g., discordance). Age of protoliths
113 alone was not taken as a grouping criteria, because the amalgamation of two tectonic
114 blocks may juxtapose rocks of similar age. Descriptions are given following reverse
115 chronological order according to their (meta-) sedimentary strata. Where bedding and age
116 constrains are lacking, overlying units (as indicated by their main foliation) are described
117 first.

118

119 **3.1. Cenozoic cover**

120 The crystalline basement of the Mérida Massif is discordantly covered by a wide
121 variety of Cenozoic sedimentary rocks. Since Cenozoic processes are not the focus of this
122 contribution, no distinction has been made in the geological map between sequences of
123 different age and composition. Previous works have divided this Cenozoic cover into

124 informal units according to their age (Miocene through to Holocene), location, and
125 sedimentary environment (Insúa Márquez et al. 2003).

126 The oldest Cenozoic deposit is represented by Miocene conglomerates and arkosic
127 sandstones, followed by sandstones and conglomerates, and then red silt and clay and
128 minor sandstones. This continental series is succeeded by Miocene arkosic sandstones,
129 which are then covered by a Pliocene-Pleistocene succession of conglomerates,
130 sandstones and silt. Other Pleistocene and Holocene deposits include carbonated deposits
131 (caliche), carbonated crusts, glaciis deposits (irregular pebbles, gravel, and minor silt),
132 fluvial terraces (rounded conglomerates, sandstones, and silt), alluvial fans, and aeolian
133 sands.

134

135 **3.2. Ordovician strata**

136 The youngest sedimentary series that is now exposed as metamorphic rocks in the
137 study area corresponds to a succession of meta-sandstones, meta-conglomerates,
138 quartzites, and slates (Fig. 5a) that occurs to the north of the Mérida Massif (Fig. 3). The
139 series is cut by a major fault, so its basal section is not exposed in the study area. The
140 lower part consists of coarse-grained meta-sandstones (quartz-rich micro-
141 conglomerates), which are covered by quartzites and orthoquartzites that alternate with
142 slates. Quartzite beds are thinner upwards while slates become more abundant. This part
143 of the series has been ascribed to the Early Ordovician period (Tremadocian-Floian), and
144 is considered a SW Iberian correlative to the (Arenig) Armorican quartzite (Gutiérrez-
145 Marco et al. 2002; Insúa Márquez et al. 2003). The series culminates with black slates
146 and minor layers of black quartzites exposed within, whose age has been considered to
147 be Middle Ordovician (Llanvirn-Llandeil) (Insúa Márquez et al. 2003).

148

149 **3.3. Cambrian carbonate-rich series: Carija Unit**

150 This carbonate-rich, meta-sedimentary succession of variably strained rocks is
151 exposed northwest of Merida town (Fig. 3), around the Carija hill. Strain is concentrated
152 along its basal boundary (Fig. 5b) and decreases progressively upwards. The lower part
153 consists of black calc-schists that rest below a series in which fine-grained, banded grey-
154 white marbles alternate with fine-grained dark grey-light grey dolomitic marbles and
155 yellow-brown marbles. This series has been ascribed to the Early Cambrian period (Insúa
156 Márquez et al. 2003), and is considered correlative to other carbonate-rich Early
157 Cambrian successions of SW Iberia (e.g., Bandrés 2001; Sánchez-García et al. 2010).

158

159 **3.4. Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit: Serie Negra Group (Montemolín Formation)**

160 This unit comprises metasedimentary and metaigneous rocks, in which mafic,
161 intermediate, and felsic components are recognized. The metasedimentary series includes
162 schists (Fig. 5c), grey metagreywackes, black quartzites (Fig. 5d), and black schists.
163 Black schists and quartzites occur as decimeter- to meter-scale lenses within the other
164 schists and metagreywackes, while the latter are featured by cm- to mm-scale
165 compositional layering that alternates finer and coarser grained rocks (relict of
166 sedimentary bedding). Metabasites can be found as fine-grained, lens-shaped (meter-
167 scale) bodies dispersed over the metasedimentary series (Fig. 5e). Former regional studies
168 identified this series as a correlative to a section of the Serie Negra Group (Bandrés 2001).
169 Its primary immature nature (as inferred from greywackic composition), along with its
170 mafic rocks, suggest it could be equivalent to the lower (and older) member of such group,
171 regionally referred to as Montemolín Formation (Eguíluz 1987).

172 The sedimentary series was the host to a compositionally complex variety of
173 intrusive igneous rocks. The (finer-grained) metabasites cited above can be distinguished

174 from metagabbros that occur as coarser-grained rocks in larger patches and which are
175 spatially associated with metatonalites. Some metagabbros preserve a primary
176 (equigranular) igneous texture. Differences in grain size between the latter and fine-
177 grained metabasites are not observed in high strain zones. Therefore, current differences
178 in grain size may be related to its primary texture (basalts/microgabbros vs. gabbros).
179 Metatonalites, metagranodiorites (Fig. 5f), and metagranites (Fig. 6a) occur as variably
180 strained, kilometer-scale bodies within the metasedimentary rock series (Figs. 3 and 4).
181 Sections of these bodies accumulating more strain can be observed as mafic, intermediate,
182 or felsic orthogneisses (Fig. 6b), respectively, whereas poorly strained sections show the
183 primary texture of their protoliths. Introducing details on the range of primary textures
184 exceeds the purpose of this contribution, but as a preliminary approach, all metagranitoids
185 presented phaneritic texture, ranging between fine- and coarse-grained, and showed either
186 equigranular or porphyritic terms (more common in felsic granitoids). Varied
187 combinations of these primary end-members plus heterogeneous strain explain the
188 microstructural variety observed in the metagranitoids of this unit, in which it can be
189 recognized felsic through to mafic metagranitoids with vaguely-defined planar fabric up
190 to gneisses with well-developed compositional banding or even augen (K-Feldspar)
191 structure.

192 Being the most heterogeneous in lithological composition, this unit gathers
193 variably strained lithologies that resulted from metamorphic transformation of a rock
194 ensemble that included sedimentary and felsic to intermediate intrusive igneous rocks.
195 None of the lithologies listed above is separated from the rest ones within this unit by
196 mechanical contacts with crustal bearing, since no juxtaposition of lithologies with
197 contrasting tectonothermal evolution (see below) is observed. Therefore the whole
198 ensemble represents a coherent tectonic slice with continental affinity.

199

200 **3.5. Mafic-ultramafic Unit: Mérida Ophiolite**

201 The Mérida Massif contains an exposure of mafic and ultramafic rocks that have
202 been grouped into a single tectonostratigraphic unit due to its contrasting composition
203 and consistent structural position (see below) relative to surrounding lithologies. This unit
204 contains coarse-grained (isotropic) gabbros-diorites (Fig. 6c), layered metagabbros with
205 mafic cumulates (Fig. 6d), coarse-grained metagabbros-diorites (Fig. 6c), pegmatitic
206 gabbros, doleritic dikes (Fig. 6c), amphibolites, garnet-bearing amphibolites (Fig. 6e),
207 banded amphibolites (Fig. 6e), hornblendites (Fig. 6f), metaperidotites (serpentinites after
208 harzburgites) (Fig. 7a) and minor silicic dikes intruding the gabbroic protoliths. It lacks
209 felsic and intermediate igneous rocks, and paraderived lithologies. No cross-cutting
210 relationships have been observed between pristine igneous rocks and the rest of
211 metamorphic rocks of this unit. But on the other hand, some exposures provide evidence
212 that the foliated metamorphic rocks of this unit resulted from deformation and
213 metamorphism of igneous rocks along shear zones (e.g. amphibolites after gabbros; Fig.
214 6c). Therefore the whole ensemble represents a heterogeneously strained and variably
215 recrystallized mafic-ultramafic complex.

216 Ultramafic rocks, such as strongly foliated serpentinites (Fig. 7a), occur at
217 different levels across structure within this unit, and they are usually related to sections
218 where the mafic constituents show higher strain (Figs. 6d and 6e). Poorly-strained
219 gabbros-diorites preserve primary igneous textures (not described here). Poorly-strained
220 rocks typically occur away from the ultramafites, their strain being markedly
221 heterogeneous, even at the outcrop scale (Fig. 6c). This mafic-ultramafic ensemble shows
222 ocean to transitional crust affinity, probably represents tectonic slices of lower oceanic-

223 transitional crust and upper mantle (serpentinites) and is collectively referred to as the
224 Mérida Ophiolite.

225

226 **3.6. Lower Gneiss Unit: Magdalena Gneisses**

227 This unit consists of penetratively deformed and strongly recrystallized
228 metamorphic rocks. We cannot unequivocally recognize between ortho- and paraderived
229 components in these intermediate to felsic rocks. They contain abundant quartz and
230 feldspar (Fig. 7b), although abundance in mica varies. Grain size is usually small (larger
231 crystals in the matrix are 1-2 mm in size). Some gneisses show lenticular grains that are
232 slightly larger (2-3 mm) than the minerals in the quartz-feldspathic matrix, whereas others
233 contain mineral aggregates (mostly made of quartz and feldspar) that show similar
234 structure. The augen appearance for single-mineral lenses could derive from a micro-
235 porphyritic texture in the protolith, which could tentatively be identified as igneous
236 (granitoid?) in nature. Some of these gneisses include green amphibole and biotite. Mica-
237 rich and augen-free varieties in these gneisses are less abundant and could represent
238 metasedimentary rocks (Fig. 7c).

239 No mafic rocks were observed within these. The absence of mafic rocks makes it
240 difficult to interpret this ensemble as oceanic or transitional crust. Potential protoliths for
241 the lithologies grouped into this unit (sedimentary and felsic igneous rocks) represent
242 typical counterparts of continental crust *sensu lato*, although alternative options cannot
243 be ruled out due to the limited exposure of this unit.

244

245 **4. Regional structure and metamorphism**

246 The youngest regional structure of the Mérida Massif is a set of NE-dipping, high-
247 angle faults that cuts across the contacts of the Miocene sedimentary rocks (RP-1; Fig. 3)

248 and locally juxtaposes the crystalline basement against the Cenozoic cover (Fig. 7d).
249 Tectonic transport is consistently to the SW. Displacement for all these thrusts, as
250 deduced from offsets in pre-fault lithological contacts, is limited, probably in the range
251 of tens of meters at most. Some of the sinuous trace of the basal contact of the Cenozoic
252 cover near these thrusts could be explained by open folds. Besides such direct evidence
253 of Alpine tectonics, it should be noted that most of the exposure of the Mérida Massif
254 occurs in a small peneplain that stands 30-60 meters above the areas located to the SW,
255 S, and SE of the Guadiana river, whose trace in the surroundings of Mérida town could
256 be controlled by some other Alpine thrusts with similar displacement (vertical offset at
257 30-60 meters) and kinematics (RP-2; Fig. 3) (Vegas et al. 2012). The carbonated crusts,
258 proposed to be Pleistocene-Holocene in age (Insúa Márquez et al. 2003), affects the
259 Miocene deposits and the overriding crystalline basement (Fig. 7d), suggesting a post-
260 Miocene and pre-Pleistocene age (probably Pliocene) for some Alpine thrusts in the
261 region.

262 The Ordovician and pre-Ordovician rocks of the study area are separated by a SW-
263 dipping fault, the San Pedro thrust (RP-3; Fig. 3). Kinematics of this fault is top-to-the-
264 NE, and includes a left-lateral component that makes it an oblique-slip thrust (Gonzalo
265 1987, 1989; Bandrés 2001). The hanging- and footwall blocks of this fault show different
266 structural records. The internal structure of the footwall is dominated by Ordovician strata
267 affected by NW-SE trending, upright to NE-verging overturned folds (Cornalvo
268 synform), with a single main axial plane foliation (S_v; Figs. 4a, 5a and 8a). Strata is
269 duplicated and folds are cut by SW-dipping thrusts with moderate offset, which probably
270 represent minor fault imbricates of the San Pedro thrust. The internal structure of the
271 hanging wall to the San Pedro thrust is defined by rocks showing a main foliation affected
272 by NW-SE trending, upright to either NE- or SW-verging overturned folds (Figs. 3, 4a,

273 5c, 5d, 5e, and 8b). Fold axes vary from dominantly NW-plunging in the E and SE section
274 to SE-plunging in the W section, as indicated by periclinal fold closures of lithological
275 contacts and fabrics (Fig. 3) and by its projection in a stereoplot (Fig. 8b). NE-verging
276 folds are locally accompanied by left-lateral thrusts that are sub-parallel to a poorly
277 developed crenulation cleavage (S_v) and which cut across fold forelimbs (Fig. 5c). This
278 relationship reproduces the major fold and thrust structures of the region (Fig. 4a). SW-
279 verging folds are scarcer and tend to occur around a NE-dipping thrust that cuts across
280 the internally folded structure of the hanging wall block to the San Pedro fault; this NE-
281 dipping thrust is referred to as the Barranca back-thrust (RP-4; Fig. 3). The main foliation
282 (S_c) parallels the boundaries of the metagranitoids observed in the Upper Schist-
283 Metagranitoid Unit (Fig. 3). The Lower Gneiss Unit crops out in the core of a dome-like
284 fold, the Magdalena antiform or dome (RP-5; Fig. 3), while the Cambrian marbles occupy
285 the core of a NW-plunging synform (Fig. 8c) paired with the Magdalena antiform, here
286 referred to as the Carija synform (RP-6; Fig. 3). Using the main foliation (S_c) as reference,
287 the structure of the pre-Ordovician units comprises a tectonic pile with the Lower Gneiss
288 Unit resting below the Mérida Ophiolite, which is covered by the Schist-Metagranitoid
289 Unit (Ediacaran Serie Negra Group) and then the Carija Unit (Cambrian marbles) (cross-
290 section in Fig. 4b).

291 The internal structure of the Mafic-ultramafic Unit (Mérida Ophiolite) is defined
292 by variably strained domains. Field observations suggest that strain is more intense
293 around exposures of ultramafic rocks (Fig. 6d), being moderate away from them (Fig.
294 6e), and low and heterogeneous over distal sections (Fig. 6c). The development of the
295 main foliation (S_c) in this unit is related to non-coaxial deformation, as indicated by the
296 development of asymmetric microstructures and minor shear zones (Fig. 6c). A map of
297 the Mafic-ultramafic Unit (Fig. 3) shows sections with relatively more strain, which show

298 more effective metamorphic recrystallization of the mafic protoliths, and are
299 accompanied by tabular-shaped bodies of metaperidorites, which can reach a minimum
300 of 2 km in lateral continuity and up to 200 meters in thickness. We cannot ruled out the
301 possibility that there are more sections within this unit with similar features, but with the
302 data at hand the internal structure of this tectonostratigraphic unit consists of at least three
303 tectonic slices, each of which is separated from the rest by a layer containing
304 metaperidotites and showing a main foliation (S_c) parallel to their boundaries (Fig. 4).

305 The traces of the contacts between tectonostratigraphic units in the hanging wall
306 to the San Pedro thrust are mylonitic. As a preliminary description, the contact between
307 the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit and the Mérida Ophiolite is defined by a ductile
308 shear zone that includes mylonites (after mafic and ultramafic rocks, metasedimentary
309 rocks and metagranites; Fig. 7e), and a set of variably strained rocks towards more distal
310 sections (Trujillanos detachment). Kinematic criteria (Fig. 7e) and the NW-SE trend of
311 stretching lineation (Fig. 9a) indicate consistent top-to-the-SSE shear sense for the
312 mylonites in the core of the shear zone. The deflection of the boundaries and main
313 foliation of the metagranitoid massifs of the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit towards the
314 Trujillanos detachment is also a consistent top-to-the-SSE shear sense indicator at the
315 macroscale (Figs. 3 and 4b). The trend of stretching lineations in the hanging wall (Upper
316 Schist-Metagranitoid Unit), footwall (Mafic-ultramafic Unit) and mylonites of this latter
317 shear zone is consistently NW-SE (Figs. 9a and 9b). The contact between the Mérida
318 Ophiolite and the Lower Gneiss Unit is also mylonitic (Magdalena thrust; Fig. 7f). A
319 preliminary kinematic analysis of this contact provided no consistent results, but the trend
320 of stretching lineations within the Lower Gneiss Unit is similar (NW-SE) to that of the
321 overlying units (Fig. 9c). The contact between the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit and
322 the Carija Unit is marked by mylonites after limestones (Fig. 5b) and siliciclastic rocks

323 (black calc-schists) (Carija detachment). Stretching lineations trend NW-SE (Fig. 9d),
324 whereas kinematic criteria indicate a consistent top-to-the-NNW sense of shear (Fig. 5b).
325 The traces of all of these contacts are sinuous and run parallel to the main foliation (S_C)
326 observed in the hanging wall to the San Pedro thrust, both (foliation and mechanical
327 contacts) defining the same NE-SW trending folds (Fig. 4a).

328 Strain and metamorphic recrystallization is heterogeneous, but the metamorphic
329 grade varies vertically across structure. The mineral assemblages of the main foliation in
330 the hanging wall to the San Pedro thrust defines an overall normal metamorphic gradient.
331 As a reference, the main foliation (S_C) in the metasedimentary rocks of the Upper Schist-
332 Metagranitoid Unit (Fig. 5c) may include quartz, plagioclase, white mica, biotite, and
333 minor (secondary?) chlorite, which make a typical greenschist facies fabric (probably in
334 the biotite zone). The main foliation (S_C) in the mafic rocks of that unit (Fig. 5e) includes
335 plagioclase, fine-grained green amphibole, zoisite, epidote, titanite and chlorite, an
336 assemblage also compatible with greenschist facies conditions. The main foliation in the
337 mafic rocks of the Mérida Ophiolite (S_C) (Figs. 6c, 6d and 6e) is defined by plagioclase,
338 brown-green amphibole (hornblende), titanite, opaques, and minor rutile. Some
339 exposures include large garnet porphyroblasts, and altogether define a typical assemblage
340 for amphibolite facies conditions (grain-size for the meta-mafic rocks in this unit is
341 significantly larger than in the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit). PT conditions for this
342 assemblage were estimated at 1.2 GPa and 750 °C (Bandrés et al. 2000). The main
343 foliation in the Lower Gneiss Unit (S_C) includes recrystallized plagioclase, K-feldspar,
344 green amphibole, biotite and quartz ribbons with granoblastic polygonal texture. This
345 fabric is occasionally accompanied by patches of melt crystallized along bands parallel
346 to the main foliation. This piece of crust characterized by a regional normal metamorphic
347 gradient is juxtaposed onto Ordovician strata, which show a penetrative slaty cleavage

348 (S_v) formed by quartz, white mica, chlorite, sericite and opaques (chlorite zone). The
349 crenulation cleavage (S_v) that is locally superimposed to the main foliation (S_c) in the
350 metasedimentary rocks at the hanging wall to the San Pedro thrust (Fig. 5c) consists of
351 similar mineral assemblage.

352

353 **5. Discussion and conclusions**

354 Alpine deformation in the Mérida Massif is limited and mostly restricted to high-
355 angle thrusts that reworked its crystalline basement and faulted its Cenozoic cover (at
356 least during the Pliocene). The main shortening direction is NE-SW and dominant
357 tectonic transport for thrusts is to the SW. Given the distal position to Cenozoic plate
358 boundaries, this deformation can be framed as an intra-plate setting for the Iberian micro-
359 plate (e.g., de Vicente and Vegas 2009).

360 The NW-SE trending folds that affect the basement of the Mérida Massif represent
361 the first deformation for the Ordovician strata, but are at least the second pulse of
362 deformation in pre-Ordovician rocks (note their main foliation and ductile shear zones
363 are affected by these folds). This indicates that these folds, their local axial plane foliation
364 (S_v), and the faults they are cut by (San Pedro and Barranca thrusts) are Variscan in age,
365 and that the main foliation (S_c) and ductile shear zones in the pre-Ordovician rocks are
366 probably pre-Variscan and responsible for the layered structure of most of the
367 tectonostratigraphic units. This pre-Variscan age of deformation is supported by Sm-Nd
368 dating of garnet in the foliated metabasites of the Mérida Ophiolite (555 Ma; Bandrés et
369 al. 2004), and because Early Cambrian rocks from other sectors of the northern Ossa-
370 Morena Complex rest unconformably on metagranitoids and metasedimentary rocks
371 bearing foliations similar to those in the study area (Bandrés 2001). As a consequence,
372 the current contacts between tectonostratigraphic units in the hanging wall to the San

373 Pedro thrust could interpreted as Cadomian structures. Normal metamorphic gradient
374 within and around their juxtaposed tectonic blocks, together with their crustal-scale
375 bearing (they juxtaposed sections with different metamorphic grades), suggest they
376 represent large-scale extensional shear zones. This is also supported by the cross-cutting
377 and subtractive geometry of the Trujillanos detachment relative to the serpentinite layers
378 of the ophiolite and the boundaries of orthogneiss massifs. The current folded structure
379 of these shear zones favors a primary flat-lying geometry for all of them, and their trace
380 is sub-parallel (yet slightly oblique) to lithological contacts within tectonostratigraphic
381 units, so they should be referred to as extensional detachments. The Carija detachment
382 affects Cambrian strata, so the functioning of some of them may be restricted to the
383 Cambrian and perhaps Ordovician period. The similar trend of stretching lineations
384 within extensional shear zones and their hanging wall and footwall blocks and the
385 continuity between planar fabrics suggest these Cadomian structures were probably
386 developed during the same deformation event. Opposed kinematics between the
387 Trujillanos and Carija detachments, and the dome structure in the Lower Gneiss Unit
388 favor a model of bivergent extension dominated by NW-SE lateral flow.

389 The dome-like structure cored by the Lower Gneiss Unit should result from the
390 interference between two fold sets. The younger set explains the elongate NW-SE shape
391 of the dome. It is Variscan and related to contraction, as its axial plane parallels the
392 Variscan axial plane foliation (S_v). The older set must be pre-Variscan (Cadomian) and
393 its trend, according to the type-2 fold interference, should be orthogonal to superimposed
394 Variscan folds. The largest identifiable fold of the Cadomian set is the open antiform (as
395 inferred from the dome structure) that separated Cadomian nappes in the W from
396 Cadomian nappes in the E, i.e. rocks affected by the Trujillanos detachment from rocks
397 affected by the Carija detachment. Other minor folds of this set can be deduced from the

398 ellipsoidal pattern of poles to Cadomian foliations (S_C) observed in stereographic
399 projection (Fig. 8b), which results from the interference between Variscan and Cadomian
400 folds with orthogonal axial planes. The lack of foliation parallel to Cadomian axial planes
401 suggests this type of folds resulted from bending (crustal upwarping) during extension, a
402 process that fits well into the bivergent nature of late Cadomian extensional structures
403 that affected the study area (note Cadomian folds trend normal to the extensional flow
404 inferred for the detachments; Fig. 9).

405 Previous models proposed that the mafic rocks of our Mafic-ultramafic Unit
406 represent the foundations of an immature arc. Such model is based on the calc-alkaline
407 geochemistry of the metagneous rocks of the region plus isotopic data, and on the
408 assumption that the entire set of rocks represents a single tectonic block (Bandrés et al.
409 2004). The current regional boundaries between all of the pre-Ordovician
410 lithostratigraphic units are mechanical and crustal-bearing (formerly assumed as
411 intrusive). Some of these contacts could reflect the functioning of rather different faults
412 through time, which may explain part of their kinematic complexity observed in a
413 preliminary analysis. In this sense, the Mafic-ultramafic Unit of the Mérida Massif
414 separates two continental crustal blocks, each of them made by a different set of rocks,
415 according to their lithostratigraphy. The internal structure of the mafic-ultramafic
416 ensemble is defined by tectonic slices, including several layers of serpentinites at different
417 structural position. The Lower Gneiss Unit lacks of mafic rocks, and yet it rests below
418 hundreds of meters of mafic and ultramafic rocks. If the mafic-ultramafic ensemble is to
419 represent the lower sections of an arc-related batholith (Bandrés et al. 2004), the lack of
420 mafic rocks in the units underneath is likely due to their subsequent tectonic juxtaposition
421 via underthrusting beneath the mafic ensemble. This idea, together with the qualitative
422 strain distribution within the Mafic-ultramafic Unit, could also explain the internal

423 repetition of the metaperidotites as the result of thrust imbricates (Figs. 3 and 4). Overall,
424 there is no reason to consider the entire set of pre-Ordovician rocks as a single tectonic
425 block prior to Ordovician times, and the mafic-ultramafic ensemble emerges as a good
426 candidate to represent a suture zone. This model does not conflict with the arc-related
427 nature of any of the rocks on the region, but implies the development of an accretionary
428 thrust (now observed as a major shear zone) within an arc-setting to close (suture) a
429 marginal basin.

430 The recognition of a full, non-modified section of an ophiolite is rare in the
431 geological record. Most of the ophiolitic ensembles lack of some or many parts from a
432 typical sequence (e.g., Munhá et al. 1986; Díaz García et al. 1999; Arenas et al. 2007;
433 Sánchez Martínez et al. 2007; Sánchez Martínez et al. 2012; Arenas et al. 2018), or these
434 parts could even occupy anomalous structural position due to superimposed deformation.
435 The Mafic-ultramafic Unit of the Mérida Massif includes most of the lithologies expected
436 for the lower part of an ophiolite. However, a layer containing metaperidotites is several
437 times repeated, thus occupying different structural positions within the mafic-ultramafic
438 ensemble relative to sections dominated by metagabbros and amphibolites. Such layout
439 is compatible with the internal structure of the mafic-ultramafic ensemble as derived from
440 tectonic imbrication of lower sections of an ophiolitic ensemble (Mérida Ophiolite).
441 Based on geochronological and geochemical grounds, previous works suggested a
442 Cadomian active setting for the generation of the mafic protoliths of this ensemble
443 (Bandrés et al. 2004). Combining our new interpretation for the regional geology of this
444 massif with these data allows us to propose an Ediacaran suprasubduction zone marginal
445 basin setting for the generation of the Mérida Ophiolite that, as commonly observed in
446 suprasubduction zone ophiolites (Pearce et al. 1984), has the geochemical features of
447 island arcs (note negative anomalies in Ti, Nb and Ta relative to REE and other distinctive

448 arc signatures such as those observed in elemental ratios like Zr/Nb and Ba/Nb; Bandrés
449 et al. 2004) but the structure of oceanic crust (layered structure made of ultramafics,
450 massive gabbros, banded gabbros, dikes, etc.; see description in this work).

451 Should the current upper boundary of the Mérida Ophiolite be a pre-Ordovician
452 extensional fault (Trujillanos detachment), the suture zone this mafic-ultramafic unit
453 represents must be Cadomian in age. The current juxtaposition of tectonostratigraphic
454 units in the Mérida Massif suggests a large-scale nappe structure affecting this suture,
455 where the Lower Gneiss Unit would represent the lower plate, and the Mérida Ophiolite
456 would account for oceanic or transitional lithosphere located at the base of the upper plate,
457 here represented by the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit. This way, the primary upper
458 and lower boundaries of the Mérida Ophiolite could be Cadomian accretionary thrusts,
459 the current nappe structure being the result of a late Cadomian extensional event that
460 affected previously thickened crust built at the expense of basal tectonic accretion (peak
461 metamorphic conditions for the Mérida Ophiolite suggest lower crust depth). The root of
462 the suture zone represented by the Mérida Ophiolite is not exposed in the study area, as
463 its lower plate (Lower Gneiss Unit) occurs in a tectonic window. This supports a pre-
464 Variscan low-dipping geometry for the thrust sheets involved in the suture zone (e.g.
465 Magdalena thrust; Fig. 4b), some of the tectonostratigraphic units being allochthonous
466 terranes. The primary geometry of the main accretionary thrusts (e.g., imbricates in the
467 Merida Ophiolite) can be inferred from the distribution of cutoffs along the SE-dipping
468 Trujillanos detachment. Cutoffs for the same thrust seem to be aligned to a trend that
469 ranges between E-W and NE-SW. Crosscutting relationships between the trace of the
470 Trujillanos detachment and the trace of Cadomian thrusts indicate that the primary
471 geometry of the thrusts was less inclined to the S and SE than the detachment. Overall, a
472 primary S-directed component of dip can be deduced for the Cadomian thrusts.

473 The sequence and broad timing of tectonic events recognized for the building of
474 the Mérida Massif fit well into the regional geology of SW Iberia. The Cadomian suture
475 zone and nappe structure identified in the Mérida Massif add to the evidence of Cadomian
476 tectonics in southern Europe (Pieren et al. 1987; Quesada 1990; Eguíluz et al. 2001;
477 Bandres et al. 2002; Simancas et al. 2004; Díaz García 2006; Pereira et al. 2012; Díez
478 Fernández et al. 2019), which is tightly connected to subduction-accretion processes in
479 the periphery of the African margin of Gondwana (Bandrés et al. 2004; Linnemann et al.
480 2008; Fuenlabrada et al. 2012; Sánchez Lorda et al. 2014; Henriques et al. 2015; Orejana
481 et al. 2015; Arenas et al. 2018; Rojo-Pérez et al. 2019). This section of the margin was
482 subjected to alternating stages of compression and extension, depending on the coupling
483 state between upper and lower plate (Díez Fernández et al. 2019). This resulted in the
484 opening, closure and obduction of different sections of supra-subduction marginal basins
485 located in the peri-Gondwanan realm (Fig. 10).

486 The Cadomian record of the study area should be framed in an inboard position
487 across the margin of Gondwana relative to the fore-arc sections of the Cadomian arc
488 system that are preserved to the S of the Mérida Massif (Sánchez Lorda et al. 2014;
489 Arenas et al. 2018). The Mafic-Ultramafic Unit could represent pieces of transitional to
490 oceanic lithosphere of a marginal basin that opened during a stage of extension (Fig. 10a).
491 The marginal basins were closed upon superimposed contraction, and some parts of them
492 were obducted and/or accreted to nearby sections of the arc system (Fig. 10b). Given the
493 deep-seated nature of the rocks of the Mafic-Ultramafic Unit (peak-P around 1.2 GPa),
494 the Ediacaran rocks of the Mérida Massif were involved in a setting dominated by
495 accretion. Local subduction polarity for this event is yet uncertain, but a S-directed
496 component of dip has been deduced for the Cadomian accretionary thrusts. The regional
497 background may provide further clues. The fore-arc sections were obducted onto more

498 internal sections of the arc system (Díez Fernández et al. 2019), making the latter a
499 thicker, more buoyant and less subductable pieces of lithosphere compared to the sections
500 located farther inboard, thus favoring outboard-directed subduction polarity for the
501 closure of more internal marginal basins (Fig. 10b). A new pulse of extension triggered
502 the exhumation of deep-seated rocks, which was conducted by (likely) paired extensional
503 faults that operated to the scale of the crust and brought upwards the roots of the former
504 accretionary system, probably over the cores of large antiformal (dome) structures (Fig.
505 10c).

506 Variscan deformation in the Mérida Massif reworked but did not reactivate major
507 Cadomian structures such as accretionary faults and extensional detachments, which are
508 now folded and cut by Variscan faults. In this regard, late Cadomian extension can be
509 observed as a transitional stage to the Variscan cycle, but most importantly, as a
510 contributor to the stabilization (cratonization) of orogenic crust before subsequent
511 deformation.

512 Our work presents a case example that adds evidence to the notion that the
513 lithosphere of the Iberian domain of Gondwana was constructed not only by the
514 functioning of large-scale accretionary faults and tectonic transport of allochthonous
515 terranes during the Variscan Orogeny (e.g., Ribeiro et al. 2007; Martínez Catalán et al.
516 2009; Díez Fernández et al. 2016), but also during the Cadomian Orogeny (e.g., Abalos
517 et al. 1991; Díez Fernández et al. 2019).

518

519 **Data availability**

520 The data is directly accessible through the published text and figures.

521

522 **Author contribution**

523 RDF, RA and ERP designed the mapping campaign and carried it out. RDF
524 delineated the maps (Figures 2 and 3) and draw the cross-sections (Figure 4). All authors
525 discussed and interpreted the data and prepared the manuscript.

526

527 **Declaration of interest**

528 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

529

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533

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793

794 **Figure captions**

795 Figure 1: Zonation of the Variscan Orogen after Díez Fernández and Arenas (2015).
796 Location of the study area is indicated. Location of map in Figure 2 is indicated.

797

798 Figure 2: Regional geological map of the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain showing the
799 location of the Mérida Massif. Location of map in Figure 3 is indicated.

800

801 Figure 3: Geological map showing the distribution of tectonostratigraphic units of the
802 Mérida Massif.

803

804 Figure 4: Cross sections showing the current structure of the tectonostratigraphic units of
805 the Mérida Massif. (a) Cross section normal to the trace of Variscan folds and faults. (b)
806 Cross section subparallel to shear direction of Cadomian shear zones and showing the
807 Cadomian nappe pile of the Mérida Massif. Cenozoic cover is not represented.

808

809 Figure 5: (a) Quartzite and slate beds of the Ordovician series in the northern part of the
810 Mérida Massif. White lines indicate bedding (S_0), while red lines indicate oblique
811 Variscan foliation (S_V). (b) Highly strained marble at the base of the Carija Unit (Carija
812 detachment). Note top-to-the-NW kinematic criteria such as sigma and boudinaged
813 structures after stretched lighter limestone bands (red indicators) as well as later

814 extensional shear bands (C'-planes in black). (c) Folded main foliation in schists from
815 the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit (blue lines). Axial planes (red lines) are parallel to
816 Variscan foliation (S_V) and show similar strike to left-lateral faults (white lines). (d)
817 Variscan antiform (hinge line in red) affecting bedding, main foliation and lineation
818 (blue line) of black quartzites from the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit. (e) Fine-
819 grained metabasite from the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit (main foliation in blue).
820 (f) Poorly strained meta-granodiorite from the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit.

821

822 Figure 6: (a) Main foliation (blue line) in moderately strained felsic to intermediate
823 metagranite from the Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit. Note penetrative fracture
824 network (dark bands) affecting the protolith. (b) Felsic orthogneisses from the Upper
825 Schist-Metagranitoid Unit. (c) Coarse-grained gabbros and crosscutting doleritic dikes
826 affected by heterogeneous strain in the Mérida Ophiolite. Note progressive and
827 heterogeneous transformation of gabbro into foliated amphibolite along dextral shear
828 zones (blue lines). (d) Banded and cumulate metagabbros from the Mérida Ophiolite.
829 Moderately strained section showing penetrative foliation (blue line). (e) Garnet-bearing
830 amphibolites with penetrative foliation (blue lines) from the Mérida Ophiolite. A
831 sample of banded amphibolites is shown in the lower left corner. (f) Hornblendites from
832 the Mérida Ophiolite (field exposure in the background).

833

834 Figure 7: (a) Metaperidotite (metaharzburgite) from the Mérida Ophiolite consisting of
835 serpentine pseudomorphs after olivine (>60%) and lesser amounts of strongly
836 serpentinized orthopyroxene (cross polarizers to the right; Ol: serpentinized olivine;
837 OPx: serpentinized orthopyroxene). (b) Orthogneiss from the Lower Gneiss Unit
838 (Magdalena Unit). Main foliation in blue. (c) Biotite-rich gneiss with penetrative

839 foliation (blue line) from the Lower Gneiss Unit (Magdalena Unit). (d) High-angle
840 Alpine thrust juxtaposing the crystalline basement of the Mérida Massif (hanging wall
841 to the right) onto its Cenozoic sedimentary cover (footwall to the left). (e)
842 Protomylonite after granitoid deformed by the Trujillanos detachment. Note sigma
843 structures indicating top-to-the-SSE shear sense (blue arrows) (crossed polarizers view).
844 (f) Protomylonite after granitoid deformed in the Magdalena thrust. Note quartz ribbons
845 and sigma structures (blue arrows) in subidiomorphic feldspar porphyroclasts (left) and
846 white mica (right) indicating non-coaxial deformation (polarized light view).

847

848 Figure 8: Stereoplots showing the orientation of planar fabrics of the Mérida Massif. (a)
849 Bedding and Variscan axial plane foliation in the Ordovician folded series, with
850 calculation of fold axis trend. (b) Folded Cadomian foliations with indication of the
851 NW-SE trend of Variscan folds. (c) Bedding in the Carija Unit and calculation of
852 Variscan fold axis trend.

853

854 Figure 9: Stereoplots showing the orientation of stretching lineations in the Mérida
855 Massif. (a) Upper Schist-Metagranitoid Unit and Trujillanos detachment. (b) Mafic-
856 ultramafic Unit (Mérida Ophiolite). (c) Lower Gneiss Unit (Magdalena Gneisses). (d)
857 Carija detachment.

858

859 Figure 10: Model showing the Ediacaran and Cambrian tectonic evolution of the Iberian
860 margin of northern Gondwana (edited from Díez Fernández et al. 2019). The model
861 conceives (a) the development of a fore-arc basin (Arenas et al. 2018) and other supra-
862 subduction marginal basins (intra-arc or back-arc) towards inner sections of a
863 continental arc system during the Ediacaran period, followed by (b) the closure of these

864 basins upon superimposed compression over the upper plate. (c) A new stage of
865 lithosphere extension is considered responsible for the onset of migmatite/gneiss-cored
866 domes, while exhumation of deep-seated rocks was assisted by (paired) low-angle
867 normal faults (e.g., Trujillanos and Carija detachments). Paleogeographic coordinates.
868

EUROPEAN VARISCIDES

(EXPOSED / COVERED)

Figure 2

Figure 3

A A'
Cross-section

B
Localities

①
Reference Point
(RP)
(description in text)

COVER (CENOZOIC)

□ CONGLOMERATES,
SANDSTONES,
SILTS, CLAYS & CALICHE

ORDOVICIAN

a b c d (a) META-SANDSTONES, (b) QUARTZITES & SLATES,
(c) SLATES & BLACK QUARTZITES, (d) SLATES &
QUARTZITES

CAMBRIAN (CARIJA UNIT)

■ MARBLES & CALC-SCHISTS

CARIJA DETACHMENT

UPPER SCHIST-METAGRANITOID UNIT

a b c d (a) SCHISTS, META-GREYWACKES, BLACK SCHISTS,
BLACK QUARTZITES, GREENSCHISTS, (b-d) MASSIFS
OF META-GABBRO, META-TONALITES, META-GRANO-
DIORITES, META-GRANITES & FELSIC ORTHOGNEISS
Serie Negra Group, Montemolin Fm.

TRUJILLANOS DETACHMENT

MAFIC-ULTRAMAFIC UNIT (MÉRIDA OPHIOLITE)

a b (a) META-GABBROS-DIORITES, PEGMATITIC META-
GABBROS, AMPHIBOLITES, GARNET-BEARING
AMPHIBOLITES (a), ULTRAMAFICS (b)

MAGDALENA THRUST

LOWER GNEISS UNIT (MAGDALENA GNEISSES)

■ ORTHOGNEISSES & PARAGNEISSES

VARISCAN MAGMATISM

■ GRANITOIDS

— Axial trace of Variscan folds
(Overturned Ant-Synf)

— Axial trace of Variscan folds
(Upright Ant-Synf)

--- Contact (discordant)

— Igneous contact (intrusive)

▲ Thrust (Alpine)

▲ Thrust (Variscan)

▲ Thrust (Cadomian)

— Fault (high-angle)

— Extensional detachment (Cadomian)

- CONTACT (NORMAL)
- IGNEOUS CONTACT (INTRUSIVE)
- THRUST (ALPINE)
- THRUST (VARISCAN)
- THRUST (CADOMIAN) (UNRESOLVED KINEMATICS)
- EXTENSIONAL DETACHMENT (CADOMIAN)

- CADOMIAN FOLIATION (S_c)
- VARISCAN FOLIATION (S_v)

